

TRENDS AND PRINCIPLES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CURRICULUMS IN HOSPITALITY AND TOURISM IN MASTER STUDIES**Malania E.,***Doctor of Techniques**Associate Professor of Georgian Technical University**Tbilisi, Georgia***Chechelashvili M.***Doctor of Economics (Ph. D.)**Associate Professor of Georgian Technical University*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7738712>**Abstract**

The authors note that Georgia, with its distinctive history, diversity of world cultural heritage sites, and richness of natural and recreational resources, has a significant potential for the development of inbound and domestic tourism and hospitality. However, according to the authors, this potential is far from being fully used. It described several limiting factors in sufficient detail in the article - these are the insufficient development of transport infrastructure, the lack of 3-star hotels, and the non-compliance with world standards of service in the Georgian tourism and hospitality industry. This article discusses another, not an often-studied factor - the level of qualification of workers in the hospitality and tourism industry.

The purpose of this article is:

- a) Based on an analysis of the situation with training in the tourism and hospitality industry, to outline the main trends in the development of the corresponding master's education in Georgia,
- b) To position it within the international system of training,
- c) To find distinctive features in various areas of training for these industries,
- d) To determine the ways of integrating Georgian education in the tourism and hospitality industry into the global educational space.

We paid the main attention to the features and prospects for the development of master's training for managers in the tourism and hospitality industry..

Keywords: Tourism and hospitality industry, vocational education, master's training for managers.

Introduction. The study of the main directions for the development of the world economy makes it possible to identify the most important factors that determine the efficiency of the functioning of the economies of individual countries. Among such factors are the quality of human resources, compliance with the requirements of rapidly developing industries, and the level and nature of the interaction between employees and the system. The sphere is a backbone for many countries, and industries such as tourism and hospitality not only provide significant employment but also bring a significant share of the national GDP. Over the past two decades, Georgia has essentially re-formed many new service industries, including tourism, hospitality, and catering. However, the corresponding achievements in education did not sufficiently support the needs of these sectors in the personnel.

The market of tourist services and hospitality services. The sphere of services has been gaining more and more stable positions in the world economy in the last decades. At present, according to World Bank estimates, the service sector accounts for about 70% of the world's GDP [12]. For many countries, an increase in the volume of production of services, an increase in income from service activities, an increase in employment in this area, and an increase in exports and imports of services are typical. We can also observe a pronounced trend in the structure's transformation of GDP towards an increase in the share of the service sector in Georgia. So, in 2022, the share of income from services

in the GNP of Georgia was 62%, the same as in 1991 - 38%.

General positive trends are also typical for the global hospitality and tourism industry. According to the data of the World Tourism Organization, the number of tourists in the world in 2022 amounted to 800 million people, and by 2025, as expected, will grow to half a billion people per year.

The Georgian market for tourism and hospitality services is also developing. There are currently 6.5 thousand working in Georgia tourist firms (in 2022 - 3.3 thousand); the number of tourists served by travel companies increased from 2.8 million people in 2012 to 7.08 million in 2022; the number of beds and analogous accommodation facilities - respectively from 3.9 to 7.4 thousand. [6]. The number of people accommodated in hotels, sanatorium-spa, and recreational facilities is also noticeably growing (from 25 million people in 2012 to 31.69 million people in 202) [6].

Despite the financial and economic crisis that has affected our country, Georgians continue to rest in Georgia and abroad. So, according to the official website of the State Department of Statistics of Georgia, the total number of departures of Georgian citizens abroad in 2019 amounted to 0.5 million against 1.05 million in 2022, including for tourism. Here, however, it should be noted that although the numbers in absolute terms show a trend towards a significant increase, most of the population still chooses holidays in Georgia. The flow

of foreign citizens to Georgia after the pandemic remains at an insufficiently high level.

We assessed the overall situation with domestic and inbound tourism, as well as the hospitality industry in Georgia. We think that it is necessary to note several important factors, both positively and negatively influencing its development. The positive factors include the active entry into the Georgian market of the main international hotel chain operators, such as Marriott International, Hilton Worldwide, Hyatt Hotels Corporation, and InterContinental Hotel. Some of them have representative offices in Georgia, coordinating the work of their hotels in the Georgian market, while others act as franchisors. It should also be noted that most of the large development projects for the construction of hotels in Georgia also provide for their subsequent transfer to the management of international operators.

Currently, Georgian hotel chains are being actively formed both regionally (in Batumi, Tbilisi) and on a general Georgian scale.

Related and supporting industries are developing steadily. All the world's largest airlines fly to our country, including discounters; domestic air carriers have a wide geography of flights across Georgia and the world. In addition, we note the presence in most large Georgian cities of international catering networks (McDonald's, KFC, Baskin Robbins, Subway, Wendy's) and car rental companies.

Support from the state plays a significant role in the development of tourism both at the central and regional levels. In particular, programs for the development of inbound and domestic tourism are being developed and implemented, most of which rely on the region's own budgetary resources. Thus, the concept of the state target program "Development of domestic and inbound tourism in Georgia 2023-2030" was developed.

Peculiarities of staffing the hospitality and tourism industry

Characterizing the modern labor market in the hospitality and tourism industry, it is necessary, first, to note the events that occurred in the industry in the mid-90s. Cardinal changes are under the influence of the emergence and spread of new information technologies.

The availability of the Internet (and currently in Georgia, 86.5% of the population of the country are Internet users) has changed choosing hotels and tours by customers. Studying the sites of hotels makes it possible to evaluate the location of hotels, the range of services provided, and prices in different seasons.

It is possible to single out the following global employment trends in the hospitality and tourism industry:

- The rapid decline in the role of travel agencies as intermediaries for the sale of the tourist product;
- Formation of the functions of travel agents as consultants for working with tourist Internet resources;
- The active movement of middle and senior managers through hotels of the same network in different countries;
- Increasing the role and increasing the number of employees whose functions include establishing in-

ter-left interaction within the hospitality and tourism industry and beyond;

- Expanding the practice of using outsourcing, out staffing, and franchising in the hotel business, which changes the principles of working with the staff of hotels.

The listed trends and features of the labor market in the hospitality and tourism industry have a significant impact on the system of training personnel for this industry.

Training of specialists in the field of hospitality and tourism. As already mentioned above, the socio-economic processes that have taken place in recent decades, in particular, the increase in the role of the sphere of services, have had a significant impact on the education system in the world. The number of higher educational establishments producing specialists in the sphere of services has increased, and the curriculum includes disciplines that reflect the specifics of the activities of organizations in various sectors of the sphere of services. However, professional attention to the activities of service organizations from the standpoint of management and marketing has a relatively short history both abroad and in Georgia [1].

Research centers and research programs have made the most significant contribution to the development of management and marketing in Sweden, Finland, the USA, UK. Such centers operating in the United States of America include the Center for Retail Research at Texas A&M University; Arizona State University Center for Service Leadership; Center of Excellence in the Service Sector of the School of Administration, Marshall; University of Southern California; Department of Marketing Kenan Flagler High School at the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill.

Three structures mainly formed the Scandinavian direction:

- Center for Relationship Marketing and Service Management, operating at the Swedish School of Economics and Higher School Administration;
- Service Research Center of Karlstad University;
- Research program Service Research at the Graduate School of Stockholm University, a division of Operations & Technology Management Group, London Business School structures involved in this area.

Initially, most of the provisions developed in different countries, including the United States, were planned by scientists in Sweden and Finland. The most famous are such Swiss educational institutions as the Swiss Hotel Management School (SHMS), Glion Institute of Higher Education, Les Roches School of Hotel Management, Hotel Institute Maastricht (HIM), IMI chiefest Center (International hotel, tourism, and events management institutions).

A broader training profile distinguished the British system of training specialists for the hospitality and tourism industry, its graduates specialize in various sectors of the tourism industry. In recent years, one of the main areas of training in specialized British universities is the management of event tourism. However, an important detail should be noted: the leading British universities for training specialists for the hospitality and

tourism industry do not have high positions in the general ranking of British universities.

It is important to note that some of them are leading universities not only in the USA but also in the world.

Among American universities, whose training departments in the hospitality and tourism industry occupy leading positions in the national rankings, we should name:

- Cornell University (Center for Hospitality Research, School of Hotel Administration),
- San Francisco State University (The Hospitality and Tourism Management Department),
- Iowa State University's Hotel, restaurant, and institution Management,
- University of New Orleans (The Hospitality Research Center and The School of Hotel, Restaurant, and Tourism Administration),
- The George Washington University (School of Business, Department of Hospitality and Tourism Management).

To other world-leading educational institutions that implement programs for the training of specialists for work in the hospitality industry and in tourism and conduct active scientific work in this:

- The International Center of Studies on the Tourist Economy;
- Pierre Mendes France University, Economic Research Center for Public Policies in Market Economy;
- Hong Kong Polytechnic University, the School of Hotel and Tourism Management,
- La Rochelle Business School of Tourism;
- Heilongjiang University,
- Shanghai University,
- East China Normal University,
- Beijing Jiaotong University,
- Beijing International Studies University.

They can argue that the distinctive features of the global system of training personnel for the hospitality and tourism industry are:

- Applied character of training of the main mass of specialists;
- Many elective disciplines that allow the student to expand their horizons and master related (and foreign and rather remote) areas of activity
- A high share in the curricula of various types of practices, internships, and sandwich technologies of education;
- Active participation of almost all students in various forms of international exchange;
- An extremely high level of mastering information technologies by students, regardless of the chosen field of activity in the hospitality industry and in tourism;
- Poly linguistic nature of education, involving the study of at least two, and more often three, languages.

It is natural that they carried the formation of specific educational programs and a set of training courses out "in response" to the demands of the hospitality and

tourism services markets. Among the disciplines included in these programs of foreign universities, the following enlarged blocks can be distinguished:

- "General managerial" or "Marketing" disciplines, such as organizational behavior, decision-making, etc;
- Accounting and finance, for example, accounting principles, managerial, financial accounting, revenue management, and so on.
- Legal block;
- Language training;
- Electronic technologies in hospitality and tourism
- Special disciplines, such as Tourism Economics, Hospitality Marketing, Entertainment Business Fundamentals, etc.
- Disciplines dealing with private operational issues, such as Service Excellence/Gastronomy, Bar and Beverage Principles, Food and Beverage Management, or even Microbes and Humans.

A similar well-established system of world education in tourism and hospitality can be used in creating analogous educational programs in Georgia. It certainly makes sense to consider the existing realities of the domestic hospitality and tourism industry, as well as the specifics of the Georgian educational space.

Training of Georgian managers of the hospitality and tourism industry in the reform's context of the Georgian education system. It carried the training of specialists in hospitality and tourism management in several areas and specialties, in particular in the areas of "Tourism" and "Management". Among them is the Georgian State University. Javakhishvili, Georgian Technical University, University. Ilia Chavchavadze, Kutaisi State University. Akaki Tsereteli, Batumi State University. Shota Rustaveli and many other public and private universities.

The system of two-level higher education in Georgia, as in many countries of the world, involves two main forms - bachelor's and masters. In our country, the training of personnel for the hospitality and tourism industry at the bachelor's level seems to be well developed and effective. Bachelor's educational programs toward "Tourism" became the "heirs" of the programs of undergraduate training in the specialty "Social and cultural service and tourism". One of the essential differences in the bachelor's training system is a sharp reduction in the time allotted in the curriculum for various types of practice, and first, undergraduate practice.

Senior managers in Georgian large service companies, as well as in global chain hotels operating in Georgia, work mainly with ex-pats.

These managerial practices come down to either applying 30-year-old models or intuitive attempts to "live in a new way."

At present, such features distinguished the Georgian labor market in hospitality and tourism:

- An acute shortage of middle and lower-level personnel with special training, a certain part of which is replaced by positions with higher-level specialists;
- Structural non-compliance of specialists trained in universities with the needs of enterprises in the hospitality and tourism industries

- Lack of enough trained specialists of a higher level who have an international level education and work experience in foreign hotels and tourist organizations;
- A lack, especially in the regions, of various forms of advanced training for workers of various levels.

Although the Georgian hospitality and tourism industry is currently among the flagships of the domestic economy, our country in this area has even wider prospects. To reduce the gap between the level of development of the domestic hospitality and tourism industry and the level of academic training in this area, it is necessary to form a significant group of Georgian specialists who would have not only practical skills but also academic knowledge of modern conditions and strategic directions for managing tourism and hospitality organizations [4].

A significant problem in teaching service-oriented disciplines, including at the master's level, in modern Georgian education, is the problem of accumulated experience. In the conditions of market relations, the domestic service sector has existed for about 20 years. In addition, it is necessary to emphasize that before the beginning of the 90s universities, specialists in the sphere of tourism did not turn at all (there was only a system of advanced training). Therefore, in the previous decades, there were no corresponding scientific and educational schools in this field of knowledge.

Prevents a positive impact on the development of education in the sphere of service and the lack of linkage between modern economic and management concepts and highly specialized service curricula.

In the assets of universities, there are well-established courses with a narrow sectoral tourism focus. Degrees regardless of them and focusing on the development of operational skills only.

Meanwhile, the development of education is not only inextricably linked with the actual socio-economic changes that are actually taking place but is also largely supported by scientific research [9]. Until now, the level and scale of education and scientific research in those leading economic universities, where specialists in tourism are being trained, do not meet the requirements. Master's training cannot proceed without deep fundamental and applied scientific research. Carrying out scientific research work presupposes a certain empirical base, the main sources of which are the services of the industry. In fact, Georgian organizations in tourism and hospitality are often closed to providing an empirical base, which, undoubtedly, is serious. In addition, many problems of statistical accounting of socio-economic processes occurring in the hospitality industry and especially in tourism have not been solved so far [2]. This not only complicates the management of these sectors but also does not allow for conducting sectoral, inter-sectoral, and comparative international studies.

The publication activity of domestic service and tourism universities is also relatively low. Eight such universities entered the ranking of scientific and publication activity among the leading Georgian universities. The integral indicator for tourism and service uni-

versities has a very modest estimate and does not exceed 3.91 (whereas the similar indicator for Western universities is 35 on average) [7].

Education, science, and practice make up, in this way, a peculiar triangle, strength does not distinguish the connections between all three peaks.

At the same time, the discrepancy between the requests of employers and the results of the activities of scientific and educational institutions is observed both at the micro and macro levels. There are very few studies applied in the field of hospitality management models that would take into account:

- Industry specifics;
- Management accounting system;
- Models of current and projected profitability of enterprises;
- Pricing systems, etc.

In our opinion, the development of master's training of managers for the hospitality and tourism industry should be aimed precisely at developing a scientific and methodological basis for solving the most important problems of the functioning of the industry as a whole, as well as individual organizations that fill it.

When forming Georgian educational programs, it should take the above market development trends into account, including the wide representation of international network operators noted by us, which leads to the steady introduction of international, including corporate, service quality standards into practice.

It is also important to consider one feature of the hospitality and tourism industry, namely the fact that a significant part of the consumers of such services is foreign citizens who are accustomed to a fairly high level of service. Therefore, we think it is expedient to solve the problem of the formation and development of the personnel training system for the Georgian hospitality and tourism industry in the international context in several directions.

So, it makes sense to include in the educational process the basic principles and ideas of educational programs and programs of disciplines taught in leading foreign universities. Considering that several courses that are well established in the Western system of education are practically not taught in Georgia, attracting lectures from leading universities from higher education institutions is being updated.

The specific content of educational programs of the master's level for the hospitality and tourism industry can significantly differentiate. So, we can talk about the formation of specializations using combinations of directions "mass tourism", "cultural tourism", "hospitality", "event tourism", "ecotourism", "creative tourism", tourist tourism, etc. Depending on the specialization, the curriculum, respectively, may have different content, mainly in terms of elective courses. Elective courses should be as specific as possible, based on the personal scientific interests of individual teachers. For example, Destination Australia: History of Immigration Conference Center Management. This "subjective" approach makes sense because it allows students to take an active part in the actual scientific research of university professors; expand horizons and creativity; look for new approaches to traditional practical and scientific

problems; contribute to the choice of topics for the master's thesis.

In addition, many master's programs contain predictive disciplines based both on the formal mathematical apparatus and on predictive studies that focus on certain types and technologies of tourism. As an example, we will cite the so-called creative tourism, which has not yet become widespread, which implies the active participation of tourists in creating impressions of a tourist product, from empathy and interaction in the process of its consumption, and the development of a tourist's creative principles in getting to know a tourist destination. At present, this type of tourism has become the object of extensive international research [5] and is taught in leading Western universities [9]. This example shows that the most important goal of master training is to instill in students the skills and abilities of scientific and practical foresight.

Another area of training for the Georgian hospitality and tourism industry, besides providing a quality educational process, is the strengthening of research orientation within the framework of such master's programs. For this purpose, it seems expedient to develop joint research with leading foreign universities on the Georgian market of hospitality and tourism services, including comparative ones. Here, it is necessary to fight for strengthening the position of Georgian research teams in the study of both inbound and domestic tourism in Georgian destinations and to take an active part in joint international studies of various aspects of outbound tourism.

Returning to the tripartite idea of education in the hospitality and tourism industry, we should note that, besides academic training and research orientation, ties with business, including international ones, play a significant role. Thus, it is absolutely necessary to include master classes in the practice of hospitality and tourism in the master's programs, and their set should not be eclectic and divorced from the general logic of the curriculum and individual disciplines. We should organically integrate a specific master class into the structure of the curriculum and the content of a particular discipline, providing students with the opportunity to form their own views on the issues under discussion, considering a purely practical point of view. In addition, educational institutions need to switch to a new format of interaction with business, in which these two parties will act as long-term partners, forming a kind of network. Such institutionalization seems to be a strategically important task for Georgian universities implementing hospitality and tourism programs. Interestingly, the most pronounced form of cooperation is observed in foreign educational institutions that have in their structure as a basis for empirical research and student practice a really functioning organization of the industry, for example, a hotel.

Another promising direction, from our point of view, is the development of programs for double master's degrees at foreign universities. At present, in the Georgian educational space, there is a very limited range of double diploma programs with foreign universities in tourism and hospitality.

In addition, it is important to merge the status of Georgian master programs in tourism and hospitality at the international level. The certification of educational programs according to the standards of international associations (for example, within the framework of international accreditation of educational programs) can ensure primarily this. Tourist universities at international educational exhibitions, fairs, and workshops. The creation of such programs is a kind of challenge for the leading economic universities of the country. This should be a training program for specialists who own modern management tools, intersectoral service technologies, and a strategic vision of the problems of development of large enterprises, enterprises these ideas can be implemented by the leading Georgian universities, characterized by a fairly high-level economic and managerial training.

Conclusion. At this stage of development of the domestic economy, they needed a strategic approach to managing the hospitality and tourism industry at the state, regional, and industry levels, as well as at the level of individual business units. We can argue that, in our country, there is an urgent need for strategically thinking Georgian specialists and analysts with deep conceptual knowledge and ideas about the practice of the tourism and hotel business, who would have the required skills. The training of such specialists is out at the master's level, and one of the key points can be an orientation towards similar programs of leading Western universities and various forms of cooperation with them. Adaptation of established and proven forms of education in the global business space and filling curricula with an information and research component will create competencies among Georgian specialists that will help bring the domestic hospitality and tourism industry to a level that meets international standards.

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